

TRANSLATION AND CULTURE

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Abstract

This article deals with the connection between culture and translation and underlying issues in the process of interpretation cultural elements. As each culture is unique, so is the translation of a given text. Understanding differences and similarities between a source language and a target language determines the quality of translation.

Keywords: equivalent, traditions, interpretation, communication

Different approaches to the relationship between culture and translation.

The two languages that illuminate the same social reality are different from each other. People living in different societies see the world in their own special way, said Edward Sapir.

Sapir's idea was later developed and confirmed by Benjamin Lee Whorf. They value literature and art as two systems that arose from one formative system of the language. Just as Sapir or Whorf said, language cannot exist without culture. If the tongue is the heart, culture is the body and interaction between the body and the mind creates continuity of life energy. That is, there is no way a surgeon who is operating the heart ignores the surrounding body.

Linguist Jakobson classified translations into three possible types: intralingual, interlingual, and intersemiotic.

1. Intralingual translation (interpreting a verbal sign into other signs of the same

language

2. Interlingual translation (translating verbal signs into another language);
3. Intersemantic translation. (rendering oral signs into another, nonverbal system of symbols

The dictionary of synonyms offers adequate synonyms, complete equivalence does not exist. According Jakobson, not all poetic translations are complete translations.

Translation and culture

The classic definition of culture was provided by the 19th-century English anthropologist [Edward Burnett Tylor](#) in the first paragraph of his [Primitive Culture](#) (1871): “Culture . . . is that complex whole which includes knowledge, [belief](#), art, [morals](#), [law](#), custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.” According to Tylor, culture combines knowledge, trust, law, tradition and various customs accepted by various members of the society Translation of a text is not just an equivalent, it's as difficult as rewriting the original and a complex process. This is the influence of one culture on another. To understand the translation activity, we need to clarify the concepts of culture and language, focus on the relationship between language and culture. Linguist Gary Witherspoon writes to express his opinion on this relationship: "If we look at culture from the linguistic point of view, we obtain a partial understanding of culture, and, if we approach language from cultural perspective, we have a partial understanding of language.

The transfer process of cultural elements through translation into another language is a complex issue. Culture is a complex set of day-to-day experiences, it includes history, social systems, religion, daily customs and traditions.

Social relations are also an element of culture. In some cultures, people have been used to live in a large family environment and this gives birth to the need of contacting every family member in daily dealings. Each person is called by his

name. Living in large families is not so typical of Western nations, so the English language has some difficulty of describing a word that expresses an address. In some cultures, people approach their elders in a certain way that they are respectfully addressed as uncle (“tog’a” in uzbek), aunt (“amma” in uzbek). The English language has certain difficulties in this case.

Some formalisms are also very complex to express, e.g. the word "thank you" is translated differently depending on the situation (for a gift, for a service, thanking for something on various occasions).

Translation of words relating to clothes, jewelry, and food items causes problems. For example, it is useless to translate the taste of food or its properties to someone who has never heard of it.

Traditions and customs are also a part of culture. Be it a wedding, a mourning or a festival, the history behind it, its significance, hidden symbolism makes the job difficult for the translator.

Belief, emotion, as it passes from culture to culture, also change. White represents purity in some cultures, and black can mean evil. This means that culture incorporates specific things, like, cities, organizations, schools as well as abstract concepts, such as ideas, traditions, family patterns and languages. In a word, culture means the way of life of the society. It can easily change and may even disappear. Because it is only in our minds. Our written language, state, buildings and other things created by humans are the product of culture. And translation is definitely a rewriting of the original text. And rewriting can reflect new ideas, new inventions, new genres. Translation, as an activity, is an inseparable concept from the concept of culture. We can present two examples that introduced one culture to another in history. One is the translation of Buddha holy book that was written in various Indian languages into Chinese, and the second is the translation of Greek scientists and philosophers’ books into Arabic to introduce them to the Islamic world.

The art of translation has been playing an important role in the development of world culture. The translation is still ever growing and is a mental creative activity aimed at rendering the charm of one language into another language and winning the respect of readers. The concept of culture focuses on three types of human activity: personal as we think and act as individuals; collective as we operate as a group; expressive as society reflects itself.

Language is social, without it there is no social activity. In the process of translation we face foreign culture. For this reason, how much success we gain in translation depends on our interpretation of foreign culture, because translation is an intercultural phenomenon.

Problems relating to culture in translation

Every communication or original message has practical value. Interpreter should know that the message is a statement of evidence, a suggestion, a command, or a joke. For example, "I don't know" is not only translated as a statement, but it can also imply a hesitation ("Let's see"). "What gives" gives the meaning of the question "How are things" in the American dialect.

It's about a process of getting the message across linguistic and cultural barriers. Culture is a way of life and its appearance itself for the masses who use their own language to obey is unusual. We have to separate the term "cultural" from common and private language. Concepts, such as "die", "live", "star", "table", "mirror" are general and therefore there is no problem in translation of these words. But, such concepts as "steppe", "dacha", "challar" are connected with certain cultures and creates translation problems. We have to pay attention to the similarity between the origin and purpose of the language. Language consists of different cultural outcomes in grammar (genders of inanimate objects), forms of titles(Sir, Mr., Mrs.) The more the language becomes a special phenomenon (flora and fauna), more cultural characteristics it has, it causes problems in the translation process.

Many cultural customs are described in simple language. Edward Sapir calls the language an introductory path to social reality. People experience is broadly defined by the steps of the language development in the society and each system describes a separate reality. Two languages that reflect the realities of one society are not alike. Words used in different societies are also different. For this reason a language is the heart of culture.

Culture is reflected in language. For example, the Japanese usually don't use the word "no". To avoid saying “no”, they use other words or sentences.

If the Japanese say to your proposal: "Let me discuss this issue with my wife”, it will be his refusal. If you call a Japanese and ask him to meet at 6 o'clock and he says, "Do you say six o'clock?", you need to understand that he/she does not agree with your proposal.

If national customs, events are culturally unique, they are not translated, for example, sari, kimono, makhsi, kavish, etc. These are just like cultural terms and should be explained to students is given. If the special word is insignificant, it is simply replaced by another word.

When it comes to social culture, it is necessary to take into account the problems of denotative and integral meaning. The political and social life of the country is reflected in it. For example, names of the heads of state (president, prime minister) or parliament (national assembly, senate) are very easy, that is, they are composed of international or easy words to be translated. The names of national parliaments are not translated: For example, Bundestag (Germany), Storting (Norway), Riksdag (Sweden), Eduskunta (Finland), Knesset (Israel), Duma (Russia), Oliy Majlis (Uzbekistan). These names are written as it is for administrative purposes. The names of ministries are literally translated according to their correct description. For example, "Treasury" means “moliya vazirligi” in uzbek; "Home office" –“ichki ishlar vazirligi”, etc.

Thus, one of the most difficult problems a translator faces is to find the lexical

equivalent of objects or events. A translator compares not only two languages, but two cultures. Due to cultural differences, there may not be lexical equivalent in the target language for the concepts in the source language. It may be attributed to the differences in geography, customs, beliefs, worldviews and others. It is necessary for a translator to find a new way and methods to express concepts.

Conclusion

Translation is an intellectual activity that continues to thrive by drawing inspiration from source-language fiction and communicating that inspiration, or at least appreciation, to target-language readers. Historical awareness is an essential requirement for translators of works from foreign cultures. A thorough knowledge of a foreign language, its vocabulary and grammar is not enough to become a competent translator. Before you try to build a bridge between them, you need to be familiar with your own culture and be aware of the culture of the source language.

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